

Honeycomb filters as an alternative to powders in the use of clays to remove cadmium from water

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***Highlights (3 to 5 bullet points (maximum 85 characters including spaces per bullet point)**

- Natural clays honeycomb monoliths as cheap tool to remove Cd(II) from liquid media
- Flow recirculation over honeycomb as alternative to batch experiments with powder
- Honeycomb has higher performance than powdered packed column under same conditions
- Adsorption equilibrium data and kinetics fit with Langmuir and second order models
- No direct correlation between Cd retention capacity and cation exchange with Mg(II)

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Two natural Moroccan clays, an illite-smectite (O) and a stevensite (ST), were used to manufacture honeycomb monoliths for the removal of cadmium from aqueous solution. This goal was based on their easy extrudibility without additives and good performance for organic dyes and lead removal in previous studies. First, the influence of adsorbent dosage, time, pH and initial Cd(II) concentration was studied through batch experiments with the clay powders. Then, flow recirculation tests with the clays conformed as structured filters were performed. These confirmed the kinetics and adsorptive model, pseudo-second order and Langmuir, respectively, no matter the linear or non-linear character of the regression followed to fit the experimental data. With both experimental and sample designs, ST exhibited better performance than O. This could not be attributed to an exchange with Mg(II) overlapping the adsorption, despite its greater content in this element. Clay honeycombs behaved also better than packed columns charged with the same amount of powdered clay in similar experiments. Their maximum adsorption capacity (4 mg/g) ensures complete depuration of a solution containing 150 ppm of Cd(II) after recirculation through a 10 cm long and 3 cm-diameter monolith with the help of a centrifugal pump for less than 10 h.

Keywords: Adsorption; Clay; Cadmium; Honeycomb monoliths; Water depollution.

35

36 **1. Introduction**

37

38 The presence of heavy metals in aqueous media is cause of great concern due to its
39 high toxicity for animals, plants and human beings, even at very low concentration (Fu and
40 Wang, 2011; Ltaief et al., 2015). Among them cadmium is one of the most dangerous
41 pollutants for the environment (Wang et al., 2009), for humans being the upper limit of
42 tolerable daily intake $0.064 \text{ mg day}^{-1}$ and the maximum permissible limit in drinking water
43 0.005 mg L^{-1} (USEPA, 2010) while the World Health Organization guideline establishes a
44 maximum level of 0.003 mg L^{-1} (WHO, 2011). Wastewaters proceeding from mining,
45 metallurgy, electroplating operations and industries related to fossil fuels, dyes, plastics,
46 batteries, alloys manufacture and ceramics originate huge amounts of undesirable Cd(II) ions
47 (Fu and Wang, 2011). The maximum admissible concentration of cadmium in wastewater
48 effluents is $0.1\text{-}0.2 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ in the European regulation and 1 mg L^{-1} in American regulation
49 (Lewinsky, 2007). In many countries located in semi-arid to arid areas, like Morocco, thus
50 having serious deficit in water resources, wastewater is used for irrigation after fulfilling the
51 maximum permissible limits, which in the case of cadmium is 0.01 mg L^{-1} (Dahhou, 2017).
52 Considering these low levels of concentration for cadmium and other heavy metals, their
53 detection plays an important role to protect the environment from pollution.
54 Spectrophotometric techniques are the most widely used to determine these contaminants
55 with the adequate sensitivity and selectivity (Montoro-Leal et al., 2020; Surme et al., 2018).
56 In a recent work (Ding et al., 2019), a simple and portable potentiometric sensor has been
57 developed as alternative option for determining Cd(II) and Pb(II).

58 Several techniques have been applied for the removal of heavy metals, such as
59 biological methods, chemical precipitation, membrane filtration, advanced oxidation, ion

60 exchange, photocatalysis, coagulation, flocculation and adsorption, the latter being one of the
61 most widely used (Jawed et al., 2020). This is due to its versatility and the growing
62 availability of different types of low cost adsorbents (Ghazi et al., 2008; Pyrzynska, 2019;
63 Sanchooli et al., 2016). Natural (Es-sahbany et al., 2019; Kaur and Sharma, 2017; Uddin,
64 2017; Vhahangwele and Mugeru, 2015) and modified (Abu-Eishah, 2008; Hong, 2019;
65 Mnasri-Ghnimi and Frini-Srasra, 2019; Sellaoui et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2019) clays are in
66 this catalogue of cheap and good candidates to eliminate heavy metals in general, and
67 cadmium in particular (Li and Xu, 2018, 2017; Westrup et al., 2005; Yu et al., 2008),
68 although in most of the numerous related laboratory studies they keep being mainly used in
69 the form of powder and by means of batch experiments (Adebowale et al., 2006; Cao et al.,
70 2017; Chotpantararat and Kiatvarangkul, 2018; de Pablo et al., 2011; García-Miragaya et al.,
71 1986; Jiang et al. 2010; Padilla-Ortega et al., 2014; Sajidu et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2017).
72 Certainly, there are some precedents dealing with non-conventional filters to remove Cd(II)
73 from water but either they were based on polymeric ceramic sponges (Vásquez et al., 2008) or
74 porous carbon monoliths (Sharma et al., 2018). Very recently engineered nanomaterials with
75 surface functionalization were also proposed as a new promising solution (Jawed et al., 2020).
76 Unfortunately, the authors concluded that there are still different challenges to be overcome
77 before they can be used at large scale, such as toxicity, selectivity, multi-metal adsorption and
78 reusability. The strategy of modifying the raw material at nanoscale was also applied to obtain
79 clay nanotubes which were used as a powder in a batch system (Abukhadra et al., 2019).

80 It is well-known the relative great faculty of clays as raw materials to prepare
81 extrudable pastes, even without additives, and the potential of the resulting honeycomb
82 monoliths in many environmental applications (Gatica and Vidal, 2011). This is attributed to
83 the possibility of maximizing the contact between adsorbent and adsorbate through flow
84 recirculation while preventing from pressure drop. Being also unitary structures they can be

85 easily replaced upon saturation. If no further modification is applied, either before or after the
86 clay extrusion, the resulting filter is a low cost material that can be competitive respect to
87 materials with higher price or that require more complex or elaborated processing.

88 In a recent work we demonstrated the advantages that the use of natural clays in the
89 form of honeycomb-type structured filters under a recirculated flow may represent to remove
90 lead ions from a liquid medium (Ahrouch et al., 2019a). There is also a recently published
91 paper in which arsenic (V) removal from aqueous solution using natural clay ceramic
92 monoliths was reported (García-Carvajal et al., 2019). Therefore, the main purpose of the
93 investigation here presented is to extrapolate this strategy to the treatment of water polluted
94 by cadmium. Moreover, the possibility of cadmium removal by ion exchange instead of
95 simple adsorption will be examined, taking into account the significant magnesium content of
96 some natural clays and the exchange mechanism involving this metal that has been previously
97 proposed by other authors (da Fonseca et al., 2006). Additionally, in comparison with our
98 previous publication regarding clay honeycomb monoliths to remove lead from water
99 (Ahrouch et al., 2019a), we reinforce the investigation by also considering: a) non-linear
100 regression besides typical linear regression analysis for the experimental data (adsorption
101 equilibrium and kinetics) modelling, and b) Sips model along with the most conventional
102 ones, Langmuir and Freundlich, for the fitting of the isotherms.

103

104

105 **2. Experimental**

106

107 *2.1. Samples preparation and characterization*

108

109 In this study two different clays proceeding from deposits located at the north of
110 Morocco were employed, an illite-smectite and a stevensite, named as O and ST, respectively.
111 They were selected among other natural clays after exhibiting in a previous work the best
112 performance for lead removal from aqueous solution in the form of powder, as originally
113 received (Ahrouch et al., 2019a). Illustrative of their previous characterization, Fig. 1
114 summarizes the main characteristics of the ST clay. The physico-chemical properties of the O
115 sample are reported in depth in a previous work (Ahrouch et al., 2019b). It should be
116 highlighted their partially mesoporous character (rendering intermediate specific surface area,
117 around 120 and 60 m²/g for ST and O, respectively) (1.a) and their high thermal stability (at
118 least up to 400 °C) (1.b). Regarding their structure (1.c and 1.d) and surface composition (1.c
119 and 1.e) both were consistent with their mineralogical nature above mentioned. Besides
120 quartz, present in both clays, the other crystalline phases detected by X-ray diffraction (just in
121 the case of ST) were ankerite (PDF file 12-0088), dolomite (PDF file 34-0517) and gypsum
122 (PDF file 21-0816). These are minerals containing some of the elements (Mg, Ca, Fe) found
123 in the massive compositional analysis by X-ray fluorescence (Fig. 1.c) along with those
124 typical of aluminosilicates. In addition, both O and ST exhibited an appropriate granulometry
125 (below 10 µm), and rheological properties (liquid limit between 40% and 60%, and plasticity
126 index between 10% and 30 %) for extrusion even without additives (Gatica et al., 2004) (1.f).
127 Moreover, cation exchange capacity measured by the well-known cobalt(III)-hexamine
128 trichloride method (Ciesielski and Sterckeman, 1997) resulted to be 55 mEq/100 g for ST
129 and 63 mEq/100 g for O, values which are in the order of most common clay minerals
130 (Humphrey and Boyd, 2011).

131 As preliminary step to the adsorption studies (Padilla-Ortega et al., 2014), the zeta
132 potential of the two clays was also measured by triplicate using a Malvern zetameter
133 (Zetasizer Nano Z) and stirred suspensions of the clays (<150 µm) in an acetic/acetate buffers

134 solution at different pH (3-10), employing 1 g/L as amount of suspension (Fig. 2). The best
135 precision of the measures was obtained in the pH range from 4 to 6. This analysis confirmed
136 the negative charge of the clays surface in the whole range studied and therefore their
137 potential to adsorb the Cd(II) cations.

138 The honeycomb monoliths were fabricated from the starting powdered clays (Fig. 3.a)
139 through extrusion (Fig. 3.b) of a paste prepared with adequate amount of water (ca. 50 mL/g).
140 After drying the green monoliths overnight at 60 °C, they were submitted to calcination
141 treatments, at 400 °C (4 h) and 450 °C (5 h) in the case of ST and O samples respectively, to
142 make them water-proof materials (Cifredo et al., 2010). The resulting monoliths of 4-5 cm
143 length presented circular section with 1.4 cm of diameter, approx. 50 cells/cm², 0.33 mm of
144 wall thickness and 72% open frontal area (Fig. 3.c).

145

146 2.2. Adsorption experiments

147

148 Before working with the clay honeycomb filters, all cadmium adsorption tests over the
149 clays in the form of powder were performed by triplicate, at room temperature in tanks with
150 continuous stirring (150 rpm) using aqueous solutions of Cd(II) nitrate (40 mL) having
151 cadmium initial concentrations ranging from 2 to 150 ppm (Fig. 3.d). This range was selected
152 considering the usual values in literature (Fu and Wang, 2011). First, the influence of the
153 amount of employed clay was studied by varying it between 0.025 g and 12 g, adjusting the
154 initial cadmium concentration to 2 ppm, the pH to 4.5 with an acetic/acetate buffer solution,
155 and the time of contact with the adsorbate to 12 h. Once fixed the amount of adsorbent needed
156 to eliminate around 40% of the initial Cd(II), the kinetics of the process was studied by
157 monitoring the evolution of the adsorbed amount as a function of contact time. Cadmium
158 adsorption kinetics was investigated using the batch equilibration system, from 2 to 240 min.

159 Two different mathematical models were used for the fitting of the experimental data, pseudo-
160 first and pseudo second order kinetic equations, not only following linear but also non-linear
161 regression analysis (Chabani et al., 2009; Nagy et al., 2017). For the former, the equations are
162 the same used in our previous study with lead (Ahrouch et al., 2019a), while for the latter the
163 pseudo-first order equation can be expressed as:

$$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = k_1(q_e - q_t)$$

164 where k_1 is the rate constant of the pseudo-first order model (min^{-1}), q_t is the cadmium
165 absorbed amount at time t (min) and q_e is the absorbed amount at equilibrium (mg g^{-1}).

166 On the other hand, the pseudo-second order kinetic model in non-linear regression
167 mode follows the equation:

$$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = k_2(q_e - q_t)^2$$

168 where k_2 is the pseudo-second order rate constant ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$).

169 Subsequently, the pH effect was studied in the 3-8 range, in which Cd(II) cation is soluble in
170 water, measuring the adsorbed amount after 2.5 h of contact between adsorbent and adsorbate.
171 This time was selected according to the above described kinetic study. The pH values were
172 measured before and after each experiment. The smallest variation in pH corresponded to the
173 experiment with an initial pH close to 5 (0.24 and 0.03 units for ST and O clays, respectively)
174 while the greatest one corresponded to an initial pH close to 7 (1.28 and 0.63 units for ST and
175 O clays, respectively). Finally, the influence of the initial cadmium concentration for a fixed
176 amount of clay and pH was investigated. For this study, the Langmuir, Freundlich and Sips
177 isotherm models were employed to describe the relationship between Cd(II) adsorption and
178 the equilibrium concentration in solution. As above, the Langmuir isotherms were fitted using
179 equations corresponding to both linear (Ahrouch et al., 2019a) and non-linear regression
180 analyses. For the latter:

$$q_e = \frac{q_m K_L C_e}{1 + K_L C_e}$$

181 where q_e (mg g^{-1}) is the adsorbed amount at equilibrium, C_e is the equilibrium metal ion
182 concentration (mg L^{-1}), K_L is Langmuir equilibrium constant (L mg^{-1}) and q_m the maximum
183 adsorption capacity (mg g^{-1}).

184 The non-linear equation to fit the Freundlich isotherms was:

$$q_e = K_F C_e^{1/n}$$

185 where K_F is the Freundlich constant (mg g^{-1}) indicating the adsorption capacity and n is a
186 non-dimensional parameter related to the intensity of adsorption.

187 In the case of the Sips model the non-linear equation to fit the isotherms was:

$$q_e = \frac{K_s C_e^n}{1 + Q_s C_e^n}$$

188 where K_s is the Sips constant (L mg^{-1}) and Q_s (mg g^{-1}) indicates the adsorption capacity.

189 In all cases the solutions were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 min after the
190 experiments, followed by filtration (operation step that lasts 30-60 s) with a $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ pore size
191 Nylon membrane. The determination of the residual cadmium in the solution was carried out
192 by atomic absorption spectroscopy with air-acetylene flame (Perkin Elmer Analyst 800). The
193 standards of the calibration curve were prepared under the same conditions as the cadmium
194 solutions. In all cases, the instrumental conditions were optimized before each measurement.

195 To study the retention of cadmium in the honeycomb monoliths approx. 4 g weighted
196 samples and $1200 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ flow recirculation of the Cd(II) solution (1 L, 2 ppm, pH=4.5)
197 with the help of a centrifugal pump were employed (Fig. 3.e). A parallel study regarding the
198 kinetics was carried out in recirculation mode and following a data analysis similar to that
199 previously described for the powders. Complementary adsorption tests using packed columns
200 that contained the same amount of sample as the monolithic one but in powdered form and
201 under the same experimental conditions were also performed for comparative purposes. In all

202 cases, the methodology for these studies, including the analytical technique for the
203 measurement of the Cd(II), was the same as that described for the powders.

204

205 **3. Results and discussion**

206

207 *3.1. Preliminary study of the cadmium adsorption in batch conditions*

208

209 Fig. 4 shows the effect of the used clay amount on the Cd(II) retention in the case of
210 the batch experiments. As indicated in the 2.2 Section, this type of experiments allowed
211 defining the amount of clay (in grams) for the kinetical studies, which was established as the
212 one necessary to remove around 40% of the initial amount of cadmium, resulting to be 1.6
213 and 0.4 for the O and ST samples, respectively, in experiments in which a 40 mL volume of 2
214 ppm Cd(II) aqueous solution was used. These results clearly demonstrate the better
215 performance of the ST *versus* O clay in terms of efficiency of the pollutant in water
216 elimination. In addition, and taking into account the previous results dealing with Pb(II) in
217 (Ahrouch et al., 2019a), we can conclude that both clays show an opposite retention
218 efficiency towards Cd(II) and Pb(II) when comparing the amount of clay to reach 40% of
219 pollutant removal data.

220 Fig. 5.a and b represents the contact time effect using the above clay amounts. It can
221 be seen that in both cases the adsorption was relatively fast, reaching a plateau at
222 approximately 60 min. Similar results were reported for other clays (Adebowale et al., 2006;
223 Jiang et al., 2010). To be safe and to facilitate the comparison with the honeycomb monoliths
224 (see below) the time selected for the rest of studies with the clay powders was 150 min. The
225 kinetic results were also analyzed by using the models of pseudo-first order and pseudo-
226 second order, in both cases following linear and non-linear regression analyses. The rate

227 constants of the cadmium adsorption on the clays were determined graphically as shown in
228 Figs. 5.a-d leading to the results summarized in Table 1. According to them, the best fitting of
229 the experimental data was obtained for a pseudo-second order model and linear regression, as
230 denoted by its clearly higher correlation coefficient. This result is in good agreement with
231 many previous studies employing other clay-based adsorbents to remove Cd(II) (Abukhadra
232 et al., 2019; Cao et al., 2017; Mnasri-Ghnimi and Frini-Srasra, 2019; Wang et al., 2009; Yu et
233 al., 2008) and with our own results using the same clays but to remove Pb(II) (Ahrouch et al.,
234 2019a).

235 Regarding the influence of pH, Fig. 6 shows the results of such study. As expected the
236 removal of Cd(II) cations grows with the pH and consequently with the increasing negative
237 charge of the clays surface (Fig. 2). However, it is extensively documented in literature
238 (Abukhadra et al., 2019; Burriel et al., 2003; Chotpantarat and Kiatvarangkul, 2018; de Pablo
239 et al., 2011; Sajidu et al., 2006) that for pH values above 6, Cd(OH)₂ precipitation effects can
240 be also operating along with adsorption by the clays. Thus, the previously selected value
241 (pH=4.5) seems to be adequate for this research as it allows significant adsorption of Cd(II)
242 (around 50%) while preventing the overlapping of other phenomena that can also contribute
243 to reduce the pollutant concentration. Moreover, as indicated in the experimental section, for
244 this value of pH the variation of this parameter as consequence of the adsorption process is
245 not significant.

246 In addition, the cadmium adsorption isotherms of the two investigated clays were
247 obtained by measuring their removal capacity for different initial concentrations of cadmium
248 with the same pH and clay amounts previously employed in the kinetic study and after 2.5 h
249 in each case. Fig. 7.a-b shows the result of this study. Moreover, the experimental data were
250 fitted to the well-known Langmuir, Freundlich and Sips models (Figs. 7.a-d, and Table 2),
251 finding the best result for the former. Similar result was reported in many previous studies

252 dealing with the use of clays (Adebowale et al., 2006; Cao et al., 2017; da Fonseca et al.,
253 2006; Mnasri-Ghnimi and Frini-Srasra, 2019; Pawar et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2009; Yu et al.,
254 2008) and other low cost adsorbents (Baniamerian et al., 2009; Shrestha et al., 2016) for
255 heavy metals adsorption, including our own results with Pb(II) (Ahrouch et al., 2019a).

256 At this point, notice that for all the studied variables (adsorbent dosage, time, pH and
257 cadmium concentration) higher cadmium retention capacity was observed for the ST clay
258 powder. This result is consistent with the specific surface area of the clays (double in ST
259 respect to O). On the contrary, it does not seem to correlate with their cation exchange
260 capacity, higher for the latter as above indicated. Nevertheless, considering that other authors
261 have previously associated the Cd(II) removal capacity of some clays to the exchange with
262 Mg(II) initially present (da Fonseca et al., 2006), and that the content of this ions was much
263 higher in the ST clay (Fig. 1 and (Ahrouch et al., 2019a, 2019b)), a complementary study was
264 performed to elucidate the influence of this particular parameter. Mg(II) concentrations were
265 determined by atomic absorption spectroscopy after contact (150 min) of the clays (0.4 g of
266 ST and 1.6 g of O) with water at pH 4.5 in two different batch settings, one without Cd(II)
267 and another containing 4 ppm of this metal ion. The results showed that there is no increase of
268 the Mg(II) released by the clays (118 and 30 ppm for ST and O, respectively) as consequence
269 of the presence of Cd(II). This means that the mentioned cationic exchange must not be
270 operating, at least in a significant way, in comparison with the adsorption process.

271

272 *3.2. Adsorptive performance of the honeycomb monoliths*

273

274 The performance of the clays in the form of honeycomb monoliths was studied by
275 means of experiments with cadmium solution flow recirculation. As illustrated by Fig. 8.a-b,
276 notice first how the conformation of the clays in the form of honeycomb monoliths does not

277 alter their relative performance. Thus, their cadmium removal capacity follows the same
278 relative order observed for the powders, confirming the role of the clay nature as a key factor.
279 However, the process seems to be slower than that observed in the batch experiments. This
280 might be reasonable due to the intrinsic characteristics of the monolithic design in which a
281 significant fraction of the flow crosses the channels with poor interaction with the solid. A
282 similar effect was observed for clay honeycomb monoliths when compared to the
283 corresponding clay powders not only operating in gas phase *versus* CO₂ (Yeste et al., 2017)
284 but also in liquid phase *versus* Pb(II) (Ahrouch et al., 2019a). In any case, the ultimate
285 removal capacity of the monoliths does not seem to decrease and resembles that of the
286 powders after a few hours of the recirculation experiments.

287 Like for the powdered samples, the results obtained for the honeycomb monoliths
288 were also analyzed by using the kinetic models of pseudo-first order and pseudo-second
289 order, in both cases with linear and non-linear regression (Figs. 8.a-d and Table 3). Again, the
290 best fitting of the experimental data was obtained with a linear regression analysis for a
291 pseudo-second order model, especially in the case of the O clay. This led to theoretical
292 equilibrium adsorption values (for a Cd(II) initial concentration of 2 ppm) of 0.026 and 0.105
293 mg/g for O and ST clay honeycombs, respectively. These values deviated less than 5% from
294 the respective experimental data. The pseudo-second order kinetics was also reported in our
295 previous study with these honeycomb monoliths but retaining lead (Ahrouch et al., 2019a). In
296 that case the maximum adsorption capacity of the monoliths resulted to be 1.14 mg/g and 1.02
297 mg/g, but a much higher initial Pb(II) concentration (30 ppm) was employed for an equivalent
298 study. In one of the scarce references in literature in which structured filters were employed
299 for the wastewater treatment (Xu et al., 2011), highly porous chitosan monoliths showed also
300 great efficiency to remove heavy metal ions but the capacity was much poorer *versus* Cd(II)
301 than *versus* Cu(II) or Hg(II) and the optimum adsorbents required a more complex

302 elaboration. Moreover, the design of the experiments was very different as the monoliths were
303 just placed in conical flasks, in contact with the solution, and they were not submitted to a
304 liquid flow. Our results are also better than those obtained for As(V) removal from water
305 using ceramic honeycomb monoliths (García-Carvajal et al., 2019). In that work, the authors
306 reported a maximum capacity of 15 $\mu\text{g/g}$ of adsorbent. In addition, the results in our study put
307 in evidence that also in the structured design the relative behavior of the ST and O clays to
308 retain cadmium is the opposite of what was observed with lead (Ahrouch et al., 2019a). This
309 illustrates the close relationship that must exist between the clay nature and its selectivity
310 towards a specific heavy metal, and the complexity when working with natural adsorbents to
311 make predictions, compare achievements and propose or select the best sample for this
312 application.

313

314 *3.3. Comparative between honeycomb monoliths and packed powders*

315

316 In order to facilitate the most appropriate comparison between the monolithic filters
317 and the same material but in the form of powder, complementary tests in the same
318 experimental setup (Fig. 3e) using packed columns that contained the same amount of powder
319 submitted to the same calcination treatment as the monoliths were performed. Again, as we
320 had previously observed in the treatment of lead-polluted water (Ahrouch et al., 2019a), the
321 outlet flow decreased from 1200 $\text{cm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$ down to 300 $\text{cm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$, so confirming the well-
322 known advantage of using the honeycomb monolithic design, reduction of pressure drop that
323 typically occurs in the treatment of high flows, which are usually employed in environmental
324 catalysis. Another advantage of this design is its easy handling which helps the replacement
325 upon saturation (observed at approx. 10 h after the flow recirculation began, see Fig. 9). This
326 figure shows the above cited comparison, as function of time and for two different initial

327 concentrations of Cd(II) (10 and 50 ppm), obtained with the ST sample, which had exhibited
328 the highest retention capacity for this metal among the studied clays. As noticed, the retention
329 efficiency using a packed column was slightly poorer than that observed for the
330 corresponding honeycomb monolith in both cases. This is noteworthy considering that the
331 monolith operated under more adverse conditions for the adsorption, with a fourfold lower
332 contact time respect to the column. In order to illustrate the potential use of our honeycomb
333 monoliths as filters of cadmium-polluted waters for a drinking use, we have estimated that,
334 under our experimental conditions and setup, it would be enough to employ a monolith
335 having around 10 cm of length and 3 cm of diameter to fully depurate (below 5 ppb of Cd(II)
336 according to USEPA (2010) 1 L of water that initially contains 150 ppm of Cd(II). It is also
337 remarkable that no signs of partial wear or break were observed in our monoliths even after
338 12.5 h of operation (maximum time monitored in the experiments of Fig. 9) and in acid
339 medium (pH=4.5), what demonstrates the efficiency of the thermal pre-treatment to which
340 they were submitted to enhance their mechanical resistance. Therefore, the durability of these
341 filters is guaranteed at least until their saturation and replacement, especially if we consider
342 that their regeneration is not necessary due to their low cost.

343 Finally, the comparison between honeycomb monolith and packed column was also
344 made by studying their performance under equilibrium conditions at intermediate values of
345 initial cadmium concentration between 10 and 150 ppm, and plotting the corresponding
346 isotherms (Fig. 10.a-b). As can be seen, the behaviour of the monolith was better than that of
347 the column in the whole range investigated in terms of adsorbed amount in equilibrium, and
348 the best fitting of data was again achieved for a Langmuir model with linear regression
349 analysis (Figs. 10.c-d and Table 4). Moreover, according to this fitting the maximum
350 adsorption capacity would be close to 4 mg/g. From a quick perusal of literature, it is evident
351 that this result is lower than that reported by other authors employing different clay-based

352 adsorbents. For example, de Pablo et al. (2011) measured a value of 7 mg/g but it was for an
353 almost pure Mexican bentonite, whose capacity further grew to 20 mg/g after elaborated
354 modification. Similarly, Adebowale et al. (2006) estimated a maximum adsorption capacity of
355 10.7 mg/g for a natural Nigerian kaolinite but the clay was submitted to a relatively complex
356 purification, and the value only increased up to 15.6 mg/g after further chemical treatments.
357 Also, Mnasri-Ghnimia and Frini-Srasra (2019) reported maximum values above 30 mg/g for
358 clays but they were submitted to pillaring. Likewise, Da Fonseca et al. (2006) used natural
359 Brazilian vermiculite for which a very high maximum removal capacity, 58 mg/g, was
360 estimated but this was related to a significant contribution of ion-exchange. Recently,
361 Abukhadra et al. (2019) developed adsorbents with an uptake capacity for Cd²⁺ of 116 mg/g
362 but they consisted of clay nanotubes prepared from a commercial kaolinite after a
363 sophisticated synthesis. The strategy of developing engineered nanomaterials with
364 outstanding performance has been also applied to other adsorbents than clays, using surface
365 functionalization (Jawed et al., 2020). In our case, the adsorbents not only had much more
366 simple manufacture but thanks to their design they do not generate sludges after the use,
367 which require further separation. Additionally, their maximum cadmium uptake was higher
368 than that previously estimated for lead removal using the best clay honeycomb monoliths (2.5
369 mg/g) (Ahrouch et al., 2019a).

370

371 **4. Conclusions**

372

373 Two natural clays from Morocco were tested for the removal of cadmium in water.
374 Before their use, a deep physico-chemical characterization of the clays confirmed their
375 mineralogical nature, illite-smectite and stevensite, standard properties regarding texture and

376 cation exchange capacity, good extrudibility as honeycomb monoliths without additives, and
377 high resistance to water in acid conditions after moderate calcination treatments.

378 The retention tests first in the form of powder and then as honeycomb monoliths
379 revealed a second order kinetics and Langmuir model behaviour for the cadmium adsorption,
380 after both linear and non-linear regression fittings of the experimental data. No evidences of a
381 contribution of cationic exchange with Mg(II) to the Cd(II) removal was found in the case of
382 the powder. A maximum retention capacity of ca. 4 mg/g was estimated. Moreover,
383 comparison of the honeycomb monoliths with packed columns containing the same amount of
384 powder in similar recirculation flow experiments confirmed the better behaviour of the
385 former. The low cost character of the adsorbents and the described performance increase the
386 potential of the proposed filter design and treatment setup for its production at great scale as
387 sustainable alternative technology for water purification at a domestic level.

388

389 **Declaration of competing interests**

390 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

391

392 **Credit authorship contribution statement**

393 **Mohammadi Ahrouch:** Investigation. **José M. Gatica:** Conceptualization, Funding
394 acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing. **Khalid Draoui:**
395 Conceptualization, Supervision. **Dolores Bellido:** Methodology, Resources. **Hilario Vidal:**
396 Resources, Writing - Original draft preparation.

397

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407

408

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587

588 **Table 1**

589 Kinetic parameters for the removal of cadmium on the powdered clays under the following
 590 experimental conditions: C_0 , 2 ppm; pH, 4.5; clay weight, 1.6 g (O) and 0.4 g (ST).

Regression	Sample	q_e exp (mg g ⁻¹)	Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order		
			k_1 (min ⁻¹)	q_e cal (mg g ⁻¹)	R^2	k_2 (g mg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	q_e cal (mg g ⁻¹)	R^2
Linear	O	0.019	0.041	0.004	0.869	55.34	0.019	0.999
	ST	0.104	0.044	0.062	0.856	5.653	0.104	0.999
Non-linear	O	0.019	0.830	0.018	0.986	99.226	0.019	0.997
	ST	0.104	0.288	0.100	0.933	4.695	0.104	0.984

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592

593 **Table 2**

594 Parameters obtained for the fitting to the most common adsorption models of the
 595 experimental data obtained for the cadmium adsorption isotherms at 25 °C measured on the
 596 clay powders under the following experimental conditions: C_0 : 10, 20, 50, 100 and 150 ppm;
 597 pH: 4.5; clay amount: 1.6 g (O) and 0.4 g (ST).
 598

	Sample	Linear regression		Non-linear regression	
		O	ST	O	ST
Freundlich model	K_F (mg g^{-1})	0.015	0.157	0.017	0.182
	$1/n$	0.755	0.603	0.729	0.558
	R^2	0.988	0.992	0.998	0.989
Langmuir model	Q_m (mg g^{-1})	1.028	3.221	1.336	3.795
	K_L (L mg^{-1})	0.009	0.025	0.006	0.017
	R^2	0.989	0.992	0.996	0.997
Sips model	Q_S (mg g^{-1})	-	-	6.686	13.948
	K_S (L mg^{-1})	-	-	0.767	0.011
	n	-	-	0.002	0.630
	R^2	-	-	0.998	0.997

599

600 **Table 3**

601 Kinetic parameters for the removal of cadmium on the clay honeycomb monoliths under the
 602 experimental conditions: C_0 , 2 ppm; pH, 4.5; and clay monoliths weight, 4 g.

Regression	Sample	q_e exp (mg g^{-1})	Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order		
			k_1 (min^{-1})	q_e cal (mg g^{-1})	R^2	k_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	q_e cal (mg g^{-1})	R^2
Linear	O	0.025	0.0044	0.016	0.958	0.862	0.026	0.991
	ST	0.100	0.0039	0.081	0.986	0.107	0.105	0.977
Non-linear	O	0.025	0.041	0.021	0.810	2.372	0.023	0.893
	ST	0.100	0.006	0.095	0.925	0.066	0.112	0.940

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605 **Table 4**

606 Parameters obtained for the fitting to the most common adsorption models of the
 607 experimental data obtained for the cadmium adsorption isotherms at 25 °C on the ST clay
 608 honeycomb monolith and a packed column containing the same amount of ST clay powder
 609 under the following experimental conditions: C_0 : 10, 20, 50, 100 and 150 ppm; pH: 4.5; clay
 610 sample amount: 4 g.
 611

	Sample	Linear regression		Non-linear regression	
		Monolith	Column	Monolith	Column
Freundlich model	K_F (mg g^{-1})	0.137	0.093	0.202	0.122
	1/n	0.621	0.659	0.530	0.596
	R^2	0.975	0.991	0.962	0.986
Langmuir model	Q_m (mg g^{-1})	3.879	3.248	3.826	3.592
	K_L (L mg^{-1})	0.016	0.014	0.017	0.012
	R^2	0.998	0.998	0.985	0.997
Sips model	Q_S (mg g^{-1})	-	-	3.458	3.461
	K_S (L mg^{-1})	-	-	0.013	0.011
	n	-	-	1.126	1.031
	R^2	-	-	0.981	0.996

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614 **Figure captions**

615

616 **Fig. 1.** Summary of the main properties of the ST clay studied in this work; a) N₂
617 physisorption isotherm and derived textural data; b) Thermogravimetric analysis and loss of
618 mass derivative curve; c) FTIR spectrum; d) X-Ray diffractogram; e) SEM image and EDS
619 compositional analysis; f) Casagrande's diagram indicating the extrudibility area and
620 granulometric curve.

621

622 **Fig. 2.** Zeta potential of the studied clays as function of pH. The error bars were calculated
623 from the standard deviation of three replicates.

624

625 **Fig. 3.** Image of the starting ST clay powder (a), extrusion machine and dye used for the
626 honeycomb monoliths manufacture (b) ST clay honeycomb monolith (c), and schematic
627 diagrams of the experimental setup to study the Cd removal through batch adsorption
628 experiments (d) and dynamic adsorption tests over clay honeycombs using a centrifugal pump
629 (e).

630

631 **Fig. 4.** Retention of Cd(II) as function of the powdered clay amount. Cd(II) initial
632 concentration: 2 ppm; pH: 4.5; contact time: 12 h. The error bars of the measurements were
633 calculated from the standard deviation of three replicates.

634

635 **Fig. 5.** Retention of Cd(II) by the powdered ST and O clays as function of the contact time
636 showing experimental data and fitting to pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order models
637 using both non-linear and linear regression analysis. q_t : cadmium adsorbed amount (mg/g) at a
638 time t (min); q_e : adsorbed amount (mg/g) at equilibrium; Cd(II) initial concentration: 2 ppm;
639 pH: 4.5; amount of clay: 1.6 g (O) and 0.4 g (ST). Maximum standard deviations represented
640 3% (ST) and 4% (O) respect to the corresponding experimental data.

641

642 **Fig. 6.** Retention of Cd(II) by the powdered clays as function of the initial pH of the aqueous
643 cadmium solution. Cd(II) initial concentration: 2 ppm; contact time: 2.5 h; amount of clay:
644 1.6 g (O) and 0.4 g (ST). The error bars were calculated from the standard deviation of three
645 replicates.

646

647 **Fig. 7.** Retention of Cd(II) by the powdered ST and O clays as function of the Cd(II) initial
648 concentration (10, 20, 50, 100 and 150 ppm) showing experimental data and non-linear fitting
649 to Langmuir, Freundlich and Sips models, and a linear fitting to a Langmuir and Freundlich
650 model. q_e : adsorbed amount (mg/g) at equilibrium; C_e : equilibrium metal ion concentration
651 (mg/L); contact time: 2.5 h; pH: 4.5; temperature: 25 °C; amount of clay: 1.6 g (O) and 0.4 g
652 (ST). Maximum standard deviations represented 5% (ST) and 11% (O) respect to the
653 corresponding experimental data.

654

655 **Fig. 8.** Retention of Cd(II) by the ST and O clay honeycomb monoliths as function of the
656 contact time showing experimental data and fitting to pseudo-first order and pseudo-second
657 order models using both non-linear and linear regression analysis. q_t : cadmium adsorbed
658 amount (mg/g) at a time t (min); q_e : adsorbed amount (mg/g) at equilibrium; Cd(II) initial
659 concentration: 2 ppm; pH: 4.5; monoliths weight: 4 g. Maximum standard deviations
660 represented 11% (ST) and 7% (O) respect to the corresponding experimental data.

661

662 **Fig. 9.** Retention of the Cd(II) by the ST clay honeycomb monolith and by a packed column
663 containing the same amount (4 g) of the ST clay powder as a function of the contact time.
664 Cd(II) initial concentration: 10 ppm and 50 ppm; pH: 4.5. The error bars were calculated from
665 the standard deviation of three replicates.

666

667 **Fig. 10.** Retention of Cd(II) by the ST clay honeycomb monolith and by a packed column
668 containing the same amount (4 g) of the ST powdered clay as a function of the Cd(II) initial
669 concentration (10, 20, 50, 100 and 150 ppm), linear fitting to a Langmuir and Freundlich
670 model, and non-linear fitting to Langmuir, Freundlich and Sips models. q_e : adsorbed amount
671 (mg/g) at equilibrium; C_e : equilibrium metal ion concentration (mg/L); Contact time: 16 h;
672 pH: 4.5; temperature: 25 °C. Maximum standard deviations represented 5% (monolith) and
673 5% (column) respect to the corresponding experimental data.

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Fig. 1

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Fig. 10